

Dynamic analysis of RCC circular elevated water tank without and with annular horizontal baffle walls

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Abstract—The water tanks (WT) are important components of lifeline and are critical elements in water storage facilities. Such WT undergo damages during earthquakes due to sloshing effects. Sloshing of water can cause impacts on behavior of WT and may lead to development of structural failure. This fact necessitates the provision of baffle walls within tanks for ensuring structural safety. Studies indicate that providing vertical baffle walls (VBW) in WT to reducing sloshing of water. However, behavior of WT with annular horizontal baffle walls (AHBW) haven't been much reported in literature. This paper analyzes dynamic behavior of an RCC circular elevated WT using ETABS considering without and with provision of AHBW by positioning at different heights (viz. $\frac{1}{3}H$, $\frac{1}{2}H$ and $\frac{2}{3}H$) for determining responses viz. displacement, overturning-moment (OM) and frequency. Results indicate that displacement of WT with AHBW at $\frac{1}{3}H$, $\frac{1}{2}H$ and $\frac{2}{3}H$ reduces by 63%, 46%, and 30% respectively when compared over the WT without AHBW. Further, values of OM and frequency decrease by 6% and 0.21% respectively for position of AHBW at $\frac{1}{3}H$ when compared over values obtained for WT without AHBW. Study concludes that WT performs better when it is provided with AHBW at $\frac{1}{3}H$ of tank.

Key words—RCC circular elevated water tank; Dynamic behavior; Sloshing effect; Annular horizontal baffle walls; ETABS.

I. INTRODUCTION

Water is an important part of everyday living and hence its storage becomes important. The water tanks are the liquid storage containers commonly used to store water for domestic purpose, irrigation, fire, agricultural, chemical manufacture, food preparation, and several other applications. The main objectives of water tank design are to provide safe drinkable water after extended periods of storage while optimizing the cost, strength, service life, and performance especially during the earthquakes (Dhamodaran et al., 2024). The tanks can be constructed using different construction materials and in different shapes. The water tanks can be constructed using RCC or steel due to the advantageous properties such as strength, durability, and resistance to cracking (Dhumal et al., 2016). Further, the water tanks can be constructed in variety of shapes like circular, square, rectangular, intze, etc. The various types of water tanks are categorized based on the following parameters:

1. Based on locations viz., resting on ground water tank, underground water tank, and elevated water tank.
2. Based on shapes viz., circular water tank, rectangular water tank, and intze water tank.
3. Based on material used viz., steel water tank, RCC water tank, masonry water tank, and plastic water tank.

Elevated water tanks form the basis of water supply systems worldwide and provides consistent water pressure with reliable water storage. Such tanks are very important for efficient water distribution in urban as well as in rural areas. Amongst the various types of water tanks, the circular elevated water tanks are more commonly constructed in metropolitan cities for water storage and distribution. As the circular tanks have a high structural integrity and can efficiently distribute weight evenly along the walls, they become less prone to collapse. Further, these tanks successfully withstand the outward-directed force of water stored within them and the laterally acting forces viz. wind and earthquakes (Kaul et al., 2024). According to Monolithic, the circular tanks are stronger than rectangular-like alternatives. The key components of the water tank include: roof slab, side walls, bottom slab, bottom ring beams, column/staging and bracings. The various components of a circular elevated water tank are shown in the Fig.1.

Fig.1: Components of an elevated RCC water tank
 (Source: https://civilengdis.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/safe_image.jpg) (Source: bit.ly/3YBoLqy)

The elevated water tanks have a large water mass at the top of the slender staging (Fig.2) and experience various types of loading, including self-weight, liquid weight, wind loads, and earthquake loads during their entire life span. These tanks are considered to be one of the susceptible constructions to dynamic forces such as wind or earthquake forces. The earthquakes form one of the greatest and hazardous threat to the elevated water storage tanks (Kaul et al., 2024). During the earthquakes, liquid sloshing of water within the tank creates localized high impact forces on the tank roof and walls which may lead to damages (Mi-An Xue et al., 2011).

1.1 Sloshing of water

Sloshing refers to the back-and-forth movement of liquid in a partially filled tank. The oscillation of the water in the tank during seismic activity can lead to structural damages. The water within the tank experiences sloshing motion, which is influenced by seismic performance of the tank. Sloshing is occurring when the liquid moves irregularly within the container (Philip M. and Antony M., 2020). Fig.3 shows the sloshing effect of water in the water tank due to the vibratory forces.

Fig.3: Sloshing of water

Fig.4 (a, b): Water tank with vertical baffle (section and isometric view)

One of the ways to prevent liquid sloshing effect is to install internal baffles or baffle walls in the containers.

1.2 Concept of baffle wall

The baffle walls are the panels used to obstruct direct flow of water in water tanks. Light weight panels of different materials are used as baffle walls in industries whereas in civil engineering field, the baffle walls of RCC are used. The baffle walls are basically used as an effective way for reducing magnitudes of fluid slosh besides enhancing the integrity of water tank structure. However, in water tanks the baffle walls are mainly used to absorb the energy of sloshing. The baffle walls can be of two types viz. vertical and annular horizontal baffle wall. Fig.4 (a, b) and 5 (a, b) shows the details of vertical and annular horizontal baffle walls provided in a water tank.

Fig.5 (a, b): Water tank with annular horizontal baffle (section and isometric view)

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The research works published by several researchers concerning the behaviour of elevated RCC water tanks considering without and with the provision of baffle walls to determine the tank's responses are presented in the following section.

Biswala et al., (2004) have studied the influence of annular baffle walls on the dynamic behaviour of a partially liquid-filled cylindrical tank considering varying thicknesses and different positions of rigid as well as flexible type of baffle walls for

determining natural frequencies of the liquid. Results of the study indicate that the natural frequency of the liquid decreases as the thickness of baffle wall increases. Authors conclude that the baffle walls of the water tank system are effective compared to flexible baffle wall system.

Mi-An Xue et al., (2011) have carried out the study on three-dimensional (3-D) numerical technique named virtual boundary force (VBF) used to study viscous liquid sloshing in a tank without and with ring baffle wall of different shapes and arrangements are compared. The study shows that the ring baffle reduces the effective mass of liquid available for sloshing by dividing the total domain into several small subfields. Authors concluded that the developed 3-D numerical case is a robust case in handling fluid–structure interaction and the ring baffle is an effective tool on reducing violent sloshing amplitude.

Aware et al., (2015) investigates the behavior of 500 cubic meter cylindrical elevated water tanks analyzed under earthquake loads for various heights and different seismic zones by using STAAD-PRO. Results show that base shear increases peaking at a height of 10 meters by 33% and decreasing for heights between 10 to 25 meters by 12% from Zone II to Zone V. Researcher concluded that by increasing the heights of water tank decreases the base shear for Zone II to Zone V.

Dhumal et al., (2016) have carried out the finite element analysis of a rectangular elevated water tank without and with consideration of baffle wall by using ANSYS 16.0. The results shows that the use of baffle walls in tank increases natural frequency and time period by 10% as compared to the corresponding values for the tank without baffle wall. Authors concluded that the use of baffle walls in tanks leads to an increase in natural frequency, time period.

Chaudhary et al, (2017) studied the dynamic response of circular water tank resting on ground with ring baffle wall and vertical baffle walls by considering different heights with single and multiple openings using ANSYS. The results indicate that water tank with baffle wall the values of normal stresses, shear stresses and deformation of tank are decreases by 60 % as compared to tank without baffle wall. Further, the results indicate that vertical baffle wall of 1/2 height has deformation and stresses decreases by 32 % and 60% to 80 % than vertical baffle wall of 1/3 and 2/3 height of tank. Authors concluded that the use of ring baffle wall and vertical baffle wall of 1/2 height in water tank are more effective.

Mane et al, (2019) examined a time history analysis of rectangular and circular elevated water tanks by incorporating a vertical baffle wall considering empty and full conditions using ETABS. The results show that the of a baffle wall in rectangular water tanks leads to the reduction in displacement by 14.55% for empty condition 6.24% for full condition and increases base shear by 19.6% for empty condition 19.78% for full condition. Further, the results show circular water tanks having less displacement by 8.05% for empty condition 9.10% for full condition and increases base shear by 13.02% for empty condition 20.88% for full condition. Authors concluded that decreases displacement and increases time period and base shear by using baffle wall is effective in rectangular and circular water tanks as compared to without baffle wall.

Philip et al., (2020) have analysed the behaviour of a circular elevated water tank by varying staging heights (10m and 15m) using ETABS for both conditions empty and full tanks on level ground as well as 50 and 100-degree sloping grounds. The analytical results show that both base shear and displacement are increases by 10% for full tanks. Additionally, base shear increases by 10% to 20% and 3% to 5% as staging height and slope angle increases respectively. Investigator concluded that the displacement slightly decreases as slope angle increases as compared to level ground.

Tayyaba Anjum et al., (2021) performed time history analysis on models of circular and intze type water tank with empty, half and full conditions. The results show that the natural frequency of a structure decreases by 10% as water storage increases. The values of base shear and nodal displacement increased by 4.95% and 23% respectively as water levels increased. Authors concluded that critical responses in elevated water tanks can occur not only for full but also for empty or half-full conditions depending on the specific characteristics of the earthquake.

Devi et al., (2021) investigates the structural behaviour of water tanks for different seismic zones using ETABS 18.0.0. considering the static loads, earthquake loads in both x and y directions, and wind loads. The results show that the Zone II exhibits lower displacement by 38% and storey shear by 37% as compared to zones III, IV, and V. Overturning-moment is greater in Zone V by 73% as compared to Zone II. Authors concluded that the construction of elevated water tank in Zone II is effective when compared to Zone V.

Kaul et al., (2024) carried out free vibration modal analysis of various elevated water tanks with different shapes by considering cross and standard staging models using ETABS, the analysis identified natural frequencies, periods, and mode shapes for tanks. The results reveal that rectangular, circular and square tanks with cross-staging have higher natural frequencies compared to those with standard staging. Investigator concluded that the provision of cross staging is effective as compared to standard staging for rectangular type water.

III.METHODOLOGY

The dynamic analysis of the RCC circular elevated water tank is performed using finite element-based software namely 'ETABS' by adopting the following the steps:

- A. Selection of geometrical and material properties

- B. Defining earthquake and wind load parameters as per IS code
- C. Determination of hydrostatic and hydrodynamic pressure
- D. Modelling and analysis of water tank for different Models
 - i. Model 1: Water tank without annular horizontal baffle wall (WBW)
 - ii. Model 2: Water tank with annular horizontal baffle wall (AHBW) position along the $\frac{1}{3}$ height of tank
 - iii. Model 3: Water tank with annular horizontal baffle wall (AHBW) position along the $\frac{1}{2}$ height of tank
 - iv. Model 4: Water tank with annular horizontal baffle wall (AHBW) position along the $\frac{2}{3}$ height of tank
- E. Validation of analysis results.

A. Selection of geometrical and material properties

An RCC circular elevated water tank which is under construction, located in Kolhapur city (MS India) is considered for its dynamic analysis. The tank has water storage capacity of 1,67,000 litres ($1.67m^3$) and is supported over 8 columns having circular cross-section. The geometric details and material properties of the tank under consideration are given in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Geometric details and material properties of RCC circular elevated water tank

Geometric details		Material properties	
Tank diameter (ϕ)	: 7.5 m	Grade of concrete	: 30 (N/mm ²)
Tank height	: 4 m	Grade of steel	: 415 (N/mm ²)
Capacity	: 1.67 m ³		
Staging height	: 12 m		
Bottom slab thickness	: 230mm		
Top slab thickness	: 120mm		
Side wall thickness	: 200 mm		
Column diameter	: 500 mm		
Bracing beam	: 250x550 mm		
Floor beam	: 250x600 mm		
Roof beam	: 250x350 mm		
Baffle wall thickness	: 150 mm		

Fig. 6 shows schematic diagram of the RCC elevated water tank prepared using the geometric details given in Table 1.

Fig. 6: Details of circular elevated water tank

B. Defining earthquake and wind load parameters as per IS code

The various parameters concerning the earthquake and wind loads are defined as given in Table 2.

Table 2: Earthquake and wind load parameters

Earthquake parameters		Wind parameters	
Location	: Kolhapur	Location	: Kolhapur
Zone	: III	Wind Speed	: 39 m/s
(IS 1893 (Part 1): 2014 Clause 6.4.2)		(IS 875 (Part 3): 2016 Clause 6.2)	
Zone factor	: 0.16	k1	: 1
(IS 1893 (Part 1): 2014 Clause 6.4.2)		(IS 875 (Part 3): 2016 Clause 6.3.1)	
Soil Type	: II	k2	: 1.096
(IS 1893 (Part 1): 2014 Clause 6.4.2.1)		(IS 875 (Part 3): 2016 Clause 6.3.2.2)	
Importance factor	: 1.5	k3	: 1
(IS 1893 (Part 1): 2014 Table 1)		(IS 875 (Part 3): 2016 Clause 6.3.3)	
Response reduction factor	: 4	k4	: 1
(IS 1893 (Part 1): 2014 Table 2)		(IS 875 (Part 3): 2016 Clause 6.3.4)	

C. Determination of hydrostatic and hydrodynamic pressures

The hydrostatic and hydrodynamic pressures acting on the water tank without considering baffle wall are determined and are presented in the following section.

a) Hydrostatic pressure:

The determination of hydrostatic pressure acting on water tank is done following the guidelines of IS 1893 (Part 2): 2014 and the calculations are as given below:

$$\text{Hydrostatic Pressure } (P_{\text{hyd}}) = \rho g h \quad (1)$$

Where, ρ = mass density of water (kg/m^3),
 g = acceleration due to gravity (m/s^2), and
 h = maximum depth of water (m)

$$P_{\text{hyd}} = \rho g h$$

$$P_{\text{hyd}} = 1000 \text{ kg/m}^3 \times 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2 \times 3.5 \text{ m}$$

$$P_{\text{hyd}} = 34335 \text{ N/m}^2 = 34.335 \text{ kN/m}^2$$

b) Hydrodynamic pressure:

When water in the water tank gets vibrated due to earthquake motions, two types of hydrodynamic pressure viz. impulsive and convective get developed that exerts pressures on the tank wall. The variation of this pressures is shown in Fig.7 (a, b, c, d).

Fig.7 (a, b, c, d): Variation of hydrodynamic pressure along tank wall and slab (Aware et al., 2015)

The determination of hydrodynamic pressures is done by defining them as an equivalent spring mass model.

1. Impulsive Pressure Acting on Tank Wall

$$P_{i(w)(y)} = Q_{i(w)(y)} (A_h)_i \rho g h \cos \phi \quad (2)$$

where,

$P_{i(w)(y)}$ = impulsive pressure (kN/m^2),

$Q_{i(w)(y)}$ = coefficient of impulsive pressure,

$(A_h)_i$ = design horizontal seismic coefficient,

ρ = mass density of water,

g = Acceleration due to gravity,

h = Maximum depth of water, and

ϕ = Circumferential angle

Further, the coefficient of impulsive pressure ($Q_{i(w)(y)}$) is determined by using following formula:

$$Q_{i(w)(y)} = 0.866 [1 - (y/h)^2] \tanh \left(\frac{0.866D}{h} \right) \quad (3)$$

where,

y = vertical distance of a point on tank wall from its bottom,

h = maximum depth of water, and

D = inner diameter of circular tank

Referring to values given in Table 1 the impulsive pressures acting on wall tank at the bottom ($y = 0$) and at the top ($y = h = 4\text{m}$) is calculated as below:

a. Impulsive pressure at bottom of tank wall (for $y = 0$)

$$Q_{i(w)(y=0)} = 0.866 [1 - (0/4)^2] \times \tanh \left(\frac{0.866 \times 7.5}{4} \right)$$

$$Q_{i(w)(y=0)} = 0.80$$

$$P_{i(w)(y=0)} = 0.80 \times 0.075 \times 1000 \times 9.81 \times 4.0 \times 1$$

$$P_{i(w)(y=0)} = 2.35 \text{ kN/m}^2$$

b. Impulsive pressure at top of tank wall (for $y = 4$)

$$Q_{i(w)(y=4)} = 0.866 [1 - (4/4)^2] \times \tanh \left(\frac{0.866 \times 7.5}{4} \right)$$

$$Q_{i(w)(y=4)} = 0$$

$$P_{i(w)(y=4)} = 0 \times 0.075 \times 1000 \times 9.81 \times 4.0 \times 1$$

$$P_{i(w)(y=4)} = 0 \text{ kN/m}^2$$

2. *Impulsive Pressure Acting on Tank Floor Slab Base*

$$P_{ib} = 0.866 (A_h)_i \rho g h \frac{\sinh\left(1.732\frac{x}{l}\right)}{\cosh\left(0.866\frac{l}{h}\right)} \quad (4)$$

where,

P_{ib} = Impulsive pressure on tank base,

$(A_h)_i$ = Design horizontal seismic coefficient,

ρ = Mass density of water,

g = Acceleration due to gravity,

h = Maximum depth of water,

l = Length of a strip at the base of circular tank, along the direction of seismic force,

L = Inside length of rectangular tank parallel to the direction of seismic force, and

x = Horizontal distance in the direction of seismic force, of a point on base slab from the reference axis at the centre of tank

Referring to values given in Table 1 the impulsive pressures acting on floor slab of tank is calculated as below:

$$P_{ib} = 0.866 \times 0.075 \times 1000 \times 9.81 \times 4.0 \times \frac{\sinh\left(1.732\frac{7.5}{2 \times 4}\right)}{\cosh\left(0.866\frac{7.5}{2 \times 4}\right)}$$

$$P_{ib} = 4.61 \text{ kN/m}^2$$

3. *Convective Pressure Acting on Tank Wall*

$$P_{cw(y)} = Q_{cw(y)} (A_h)_c \rho g h D [1 - 1/3 \cos^2\phi] \cos\phi \quad (5)$$

where,

$P_{cw(y)}$ = Convective hydrodynamic pressure on tank wall,

$(A_h)_c$ = Design horizontal seismic coefficient for convective mode,

ρ = Mass density of water,

g = Acceleration due to gravity,

h = Maximum depth of water,

D = Inner diameter of circular tank, and

ϕ = Circumferential angle

Further, the coefficient of convective pressure ($Q_{cw(y)}$) is determined by using following formula:

$$Q_{cw(y)} = 0.5625 \frac{\cosh\left(3.674\frac{y}{D}\right)}{\cosh\left(3.674\frac{h}{D}\right)} \quad (6)$$

where,

$Q_{cw(y)}$ = Coefficient of convective pressure on tank wall,

y = Vertical distance of a point on tank wall from the bottom of tank wall,

h = Maximum depth of water, and

D = Inner diameter of circular tank

Referring to values given in Table 1 the impulsive pressures acting on wall tank at the bottom ($y = 0$) and at the top ($y = h = 4\text{m}$) is calculated as below:

a. *Convective pressure at bottom of tank wall (for $y = 0$)*

$$Q_{cw(y=0)} = 0.5625 \times \frac{\cosh\left(3.674\frac{0}{7.5}\right)}{\cosh\left(3.674\frac{4}{7.5}\right)}$$

$$Q_{cw(y=0)} = 0.16$$

$$P_{cw(y=0)} = 0.16 \times 0.0255 \times 1,000 \times 9.81 \times 4 \times 7.5 \times [1 - 1/3 \cos^2(0)] \cos(0)$$

$$P_{cw(y=0)} = 0.80 \text{ kN/m}^2$$

b. *Convective pressure at top of tank wall (for $y = 4$)*

$$Q_{cw(y=4)} = 0.5625 \times \frac{\cosh\left(3.674\frac{4}{7.5}\right)}{\cosh\left(3.674\frac{4}{7.5}\right)}$$

$$Q_{cw(y=4)} = 0.56$$

$$P_{cw(y=h)} = 0.56 \times 0.0255 \times 1,000 \times 9.81 \times 4 \times 7.5 \times [1 - 1/3 \cos^2(0)] \cos(0)$$

$$P_{cw(y=h)} = 2.8 \text{ kN/m}^2$$

4. *Convective Pressure Acting on Tank Floor Slab Base*

$$P_{cb} = Q_{cb(x)} (A_h)_c \rho g D \quad (7)$$

where,

P_{cb} = Convective hydrodynamic pressure on tank base,
 $Q_{cb(x)}$ = Coefficient of convective pressure on tank base,
 A_{hc} = Design horizontal seismic coefficient for convective mode,
 ρ = Mass density of water,
 g = Acceleration due to gravity,
 D = Inner diameter of circular tank, and
 x = Horizontal distance in the direction of seismic force, of a point on base slab from the reference axis at the centre of tank

$$Q_{cb(x)} = 1.125[x/D - 4/3 (x/D)^3] \times \operatorname{sech} 3.674 \frac{h}{D} \tag{8}$$

where,

$Q_{cb(x)}$ = Coefficient of convective pressure on tank base,
 h = Maximum depth of water,
 D = Inner diameter of circular tank, and
 x = Horizontal distance in the direction of seismic force, of a point on base slab from the reference axis at the centre of tank

Referring to values given in Table 1 the convective pressures acting on floor slab base of tank is calculated as below:

$$Q_{cb(x)} = 1.125[3.75/7.5 - 4/3 (3.75/7.5)^3] \operatorname{sech} (3.674 \times 4/7.5)$$

$$Q_{cb(x)} = 0.07$$

$$P_{cb} = 0.07 \times 0.0255 \times 1000 \times 9.81 \times 7.5$$

$$P_{cb} = 0.13 \text{ kN/m}^2$$

The hydrodynamic pressures acting on the tank wall and floor slab have been computed for all Models, including varying positions of the annular horizontal baffle wall along the tank height. These pressures were determined in accordance with the methodology described in the above section. The results are summarized and tabulated in Table 4.

Table 4: Hydrodynamic pressures acting on water tank wall and slab

Conditions	Convective pressure (kN/m ²)			Impulsive pressure (kN/m ²)	
	At top	At bottom	On slab	On wall	On slab
WBW	0.8	2.8	0.13	2.35	4.61
With AHBW at 1/3H	0.8	2.8	0.13	2.22	4.36
With AHBW at 1/2 H	0.8	2.8	0.13	2.07	4.05
With AHBW at 2/3H	0.8	2.8	0.13	1.91	3.74

D. Modelling and analysis of water tank using ETABS for different Models

a) Modelling and analysis for determining responses of water tank

The modelling and dynamic analysis of the water tank under consideration is carried out by developing models for different cases using finite element based ETABS software. The sequential steps followed for the modelling and analysis of tank is presented in the form of flowchart in Fig.8.

Fig.8: Flowchart of analysis using ETABS

The modelling of water tank under consideration is done for the following different cases:

- i. Model 1: Water tank without annular horizontal baffle wall (WBW) (Fig. 9a),
- ii. Model 2: Water tank with annular horizontal baffle wall (AHBW) position along 1/3 height of tank (Fig. 9b),
- iii. Model 3: Water tank with annular horizontal baffle wall (AHBW) position along 1/2 height of tank (Fig. 9c),
- iv. Model 4: Water tank with annular horizontal baffle wall (AHBW) position along 2/3 height of tank (Fig. 9d),

Step1-2-3: Development of models

The development of models for above four different cases is done taking into account geometrical parameters and material properties (Table 1) and presented in Fig. 9 (a, b, c and d).

Fig.9 (a, b, c, d): Geometry of water tank in ETABS for Analysis

Step 4-5-6-7-8: Defining loads

Various loads viz, dead load, live load, earthquake load, wind load, hydrostatic and hydrodynamic forces are defined and their combinations are worked out. The defined loads are then assigned to the water tank models developed for cases (Fig.9)

Step 9: Analysis of water tank models

After assigning the loads, the analysis of the water tank models is performed using ETABS software and the results for responses viz, displacement in x and y direction, storey shear, overturning-moment, time period and frequency are noted.

E. Validation of analysis results

i. Validation of software results by available results from literature

For validation of the results obtained by ETABS software, a circular elevated water tank without any baffle wall analysed by using same software (ETABS), available in the literature (Kaul et al., 2024), was considered for analysing it for determining the responses viz, mass participation factor, time period and frequency. The geometric details and material properties considered for the analysis are as given in Table 5.

Table 5: Geometric details and material properties of water tank

Geometric details		Material properties	
Tank diameter (ϕ)	: 23 m	Grade of concrete	: 30 (N/mm ²)
Tank height	: 5 m	Grade of steel	: 415 (N/mm ²)
Capacity	: 20.77 m ³		
Staging height	: 16 m		
Bottom slab thickness	: 300mm		
Top slab thickness	: 150mm		
Side wall thickness	: 300 mm		
Column diameter	: 500 mm		
Bracing beam	: 350 x 500 mm		

The water tank was modelled using the geometrical and material properties given in Table 5 and the developed model is shown in Fig. 10.

Fig.10: Geometry of circular elevated water tank

The analysis of the water tank is then performed by defining loads and assigning them to the developed model of water tank and the results of various responses viz, mass participation factor, time period and frequency are obtained.

ii. Validation of software results by experimentation

In order to validate the result of displacement obtained by ETABS software, an experiment was performed by developing a prototype model of water tank for different positions of baffle wall considering full water condition as shown in Fig. 11 a-e and Fig.12 a-d.

Fig. 11(a, b, c, d, e): Details of experimental set up of the fabricated water tank model

The prototype model of the water tank was subjected to vibrations by keeping it over the shake table (consisting of 30 cm wide platform with a load bearing capacity of 25 kg with different rpm speeds 100-600rpm). The details of setup developed for conducting experimentation is shown in Fig. 12(a, b, c, d).

Fig. 12(a, b, c, d): Experimental water tank models without and with AHBW

The displacement results obtained by experimentation are recorded.

The results obtained by ETABS software for the water tank considering geometrical and material properties available in the literature and also by conducting experimentation on developed prototype water tank model are given in the Table 6 and Table 7.

Table 6: Analysis results obtained by ETABS software and available in literature

Response	Results by ETABS	Results from literature	% Deviation
Mass participation factor	99.85	99.13	0.72%
Time Period (sec)	2.044	1.89	7.53%
Frequency (cyc/sec)	0.489	0.5	2.20%

Table 7: Displacement values obtained by software and experimentation

Models	Displacement (mm) obtained by		% Deviation
	ETABS software	Experimentation	
Without AHBW	13.27mm	12mm	9.57%
With AHBW at 1/3 H	4.68mm	5mm	6.4%
With AHBW at 1/2 H	6.89mm	7mm	1.57%
With AHBW at 2/3 H	8.78mm	9mm	2.44%

From the values indicated in the Table 6, it is observed that the values of the results for the responses viz. mass participation factor, time period and frequency are found to be approximately same with less than an average value of 3.43%. Further, for the different models the experimental results of displacement indicated in Table 7, it is observed that the values of the results for the displacement are found to be approximately same with less than an average value of 4.99%. Thus, the software analysis results are validated.

IV. ANALYSIS OF CIRCULAR ELEVATED WATER TANK WITH VERTICAL BAFFLE WALLS

The behaviour of an RCC circular elevated water tank is also analysed considering provision of vertical baffle walls (VBW) by varying their heights (viz. 1/3H, 1/2H and 2/3H). The geometrical and material properties considered for the

analysis are same as that of the water tank with AHBW (Table 1). The developed model of circular elevated water tank with VBW using ETABS is shown in Fig.13 (a, b, and c).

Fig.13 (a, b, c): Geometry of water tank in ETABS for Analysis

The analysis of water tank provided with VBW by varying heights (viz. 1/3H, 1/2H and 2/3H) is performed using ETABS software. Adopting the analysis steps as outlined in the section D (Fig.8 Flowchart of analysis)

V. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

(a) Dynamic analysis of water tank with AHBW

The dynamic analysis of water tanks models was performed by using ETABS software for determining the various responses of the tank. The models of the tank were categorized based on the position of AHBW along the height of the tank. The results of dynamic analysis of different models of water tank under consideration for various responses (viz. displacement in x and y direction, overturning-moment, and frequency) are presented in Table 8.

Table 8: Analysis results of circular elevated water tank without and with AHB walls

Responses	Model-1(WBW)	Model-2 (1/3 AHBW)	Model 3 (1/2 AHBW)	Model 4 (2/3 AHBW)
Displacement (x- dir.) (mm)	235.16	85.84	126.68	163.79
Displacement (y- dir.) (mm)	13.57	4.94	7.33	9.48
Overturning-moment (kNm)	16633.95	15586.03	15634.94	15682.47
Frequency (cyc/sec)	32.01	31.89	31.97	32.00

Referring to Table 8, the variations in values of responses viz. displacement (x and y direction), overturning-moment, and frequency of the water tank models are graphically represented in the Fig. 14 (a, b, c).

Fig. 14(a, b, c): Variation in values of responses

From Fig. 14a, it is observed that the displacement values (x-direction) of the water tank model considering the provision of AHBW gets reduced by an average value of 46.65% when compared with the corresponding displacement values of the water tank without AHBW. A minimum displacement of 85.84mm occurs for the water tank model provided with AHBW at 1/3H. Further, the displacement values of the water tank are found to be increased by 32.23% and 47.60% for 1/2H and 2/3H positions of the AHBW respectively when compared over the tank model provided with AHBW at 1/3 H. The displacement values of all the water tank models in y-direction are found to be lesser than the displacement values in x-direction by an average value of 94.22%. The mode shapes for displacements of water tank models considering the provision of AHBW at 1/3, 1/2, 2/3 positions along the height of the water tank are shown in Fig.15(a, b, c and d).

Fig.15 (a, b, c, d): Displacement mode shapes of water tank models for different AHBW positions

From Fig. 14b, it is observed that the overturning-moment values of the water tank model considering the provision of AHBW gets reduced by an average value of 6% when compared with the corresponding overturning-moment values of the water tank without AHBW. A minimum overturning-moment of 15586.03 kNm occurs for the water tank model provided with AHBW at 1/3H. Further, the overturning-moment values of the water tank are found to be increased by 0.31% and 0.61% for 1/2H and 2/3H positions of the AHBW respectively when compared to the tank model provided with AHBW at 1/3 H.

From Fig. 14c, it is observed that the frequency values of the water tank model considering the provision of AHBW gets reduced by an average value of 0.21% when compared with the corresponding frequency values of the water tank without AHBW. A minimum frequency of 31.89 cyc/sec occurs for the water tank model provided with AHBW at 1/3H. Further, the frequency values of the water tank are found to be increased by 0.25% and 0.34% for 1/2H and 2/3H positions of the AHBW respectively when compared to the tank model provided with AHBW at 1/3 H.

(b) Dynamic analysis of water tank with VBW

The dynamic analysis of water tank models was performed by using ETABS software for determining various responses of the tank. The models of the tank were categorized based on the position of VBW by varying their height (viz. 1/3VBW, 1/2VBW and 2/3 VBW). The results of dynamic analysis of different models of water tank under consideration for various responses (viz. displacement in x and y direction, overturning-moment, and frequency) are presented in Table 9.

Table 9: Analysis results of circular elevated water tank without and with VB walls

Responses	Model-1(WBW)	Model-2(1/3VBW)	Model-3(1/2VBW)	Model-4(2/3 VBW)
Displacement (x-dir.) (mm)	235.16	50.32	70.02	88.59
Displacement (y-dir.) (mm)	13.57	2.94	4.07	5.13
Overturning-moment (kNm)	16633.95	17334.16	17515.29	17706.13
Frequency (cyc/sec)	32.01	31.60	31.56	31.52

Referring to Table 8 and Table 9, the comparison of analysis results for the responses of water tank (viz. displacement, overturning-moment, and frequency) considering the provisions of AHBW and VBW is done and graphically represented in Fig. 16 (a, b, c).

Fig. 16 (a, b, c): Comparison of variations in the values of responses

From the Fig.16 (a), it is clearly observed that the displacements of water tank considering the provision of VBW significantly is reduced by an average value of 44% when compared over the displacements of water tank considering the provision of AHBW for all the positions (i.e. 1/3H, 1/2H, 2/3H) along the height of tank.

Further from the Fig.16 (b), it is clearly observed that the overturning-moment of water tank considering the provision of VBW significantly get increased by an average value of 10.75% when compared over the overturning-moment of water tank considering the provision of AHBW for all the positions (i.e. 1/3H, 1/2H, 2/3H) along the height of tank.

Further from the Fig.16 (c), it is clearly observed that the frequency of water tank considering the provision of VBW significantly get reduced by an average value of 1.23% when compared over the frequency of water tank considering the provision of AHBW for all the positions (i.e. 1/3H, 1/2H, 2/3H) along the height of tank.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The dynamic analysis of a RCC circular elevated water tank considering without and with provision of annular horizontal baffle walls (AHBW) at different position along the height of water tank was performed using ETABS software. Based on the results of dynamic analysis for the responses viz. displacement (x and y direction), overturning-moment and frequency of the water tank under consideration with fully filled water, the following conclusions are drawn:

A) Dynamic analysis of water tank with AHBW

1. Displacements:

- (a) The displacement values (x-direction) of the water tank models considering the provision of AHBW gets reduced by an average value of 46.65% when compared with the corresponding displacement values of the water tank without provision of AHBW. The lowest displacement (85.84mm) occurs for the water tank model provided with AHBW at 1/3H.
- (b) The displacement values increased by 32.23% and 47.60% for water tank models provided with AHBW at 1/2H and 2/3H positions respectively when compared over the water tank model provided with AHBW at 1/3H.
- (c) The displacement values of all the water tank models in y-direction are lesser than the displacement values in x-direction by an average value of 94.22%.

2. Overturning-moments:

- (a) The overturning-moment values of the water tank models considering the provision of AHBW gets reduced by an average value of 6% when compared with the corresponding overturning-moment values of the water tank without AHBW. The lowest overturning-moment (15586.03 kNm) occurs for the water tank model provided with AHBW at 1/3H.
- (b) The overturning-moment values increased by 0.31% and 0.61% for water tank models provided with AHBW at 1/2H and 2/3H positions respectively when compared over water tank model provided with AHBW at 1/3 H.

3. Frequency:

- (a) The values of frequency for water tank models considering the provision of AHBW get reduced by an average value of 0.21% when compared with the corresponding frequency values of the water tank without AHBW. The lowest frequency (31.89cyc/sec) occurs for the water tank model provided with AHBW at 1/3H.
- (b) The frequency values increased by 0.25% and 0.34% for water tank models provided with AHBW at 1/2H and 2/3H positions respectively when compared over water tank model provided with AHBW at 1/3 H.

Thus, it is concluded that the RCC circular elevated water tank provided with AHBW at 1/3H along the height of the tank performs better in respect of displacement, overturning-moment and frequency with fully filled water condition.

B) Dynamic analysis of water tank with vertical baffle walls (VBW)

The dynamic analysis of water tank considering the provision VBW is also performed to understand the behaviour of water tank in respect of displacements, overturning-moment and frequency. The use of VBW in the water tank contributes in significant reduction in the displacement and frequency by an average value of 44% and 1.23% for all the heights of the VBW (i.e. 1/3H, 1/2H and 2/3H) compared to the water tank with the AHBW.

Thus, it is concluded that the RCC circular elevated water tanks provided with VBW performs better than the tank with AHBW.

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